

considerable loss in grain yield of local improved and high yielding rice varieties. Recorded observations show that disease intensity is generally higher during kharif in the cooler climatic regions than during summer in hotter climates. The disease has been observed in varying intensity at all altitudes. It is not specific to any soil type nor to paddy variety. Some varieties, e.g. IET1444 and FTB20, were

continuously infected during kharif; others – e.g. IET3626, IET5725, and IET4107 – had maximum disease infection in 1 year but were absolutely free from the disease during subsequent years. Thus, it is difficult to judge a variety for its susceptibility.

The studies on disease control by seed treatment carried out for several years at the RRS indicate that only the hot-water

treatment at 54°C for 20 minutes gives good control. Other studies carried out with systemic fungicides indicate that carboxin and carbendazim are second to the hot-water treatment in checking the seedborne infection.

Further detailed investigations on the etiology of the causal organism and its mode of infection are needed to understand the disease. ■

Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) Beauv. — a new host for *Rhynchosporium oryzae
Hashioka and Yokogi

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During a search for collateral hosts of *Rhynchosporium oryzae* (the causal organism of rice leaf scald disease) severe leaf scald disease was observed in October 1978 at Takyel, Manipur, on the leaves of the graminaceous weed *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) Beauv. The weed was growing in a field of the local

2. Fungal growth on the PDE.

rice variety Chahao, which was also severely infected. The typical light- to dark-brown zonate symptoms identical to those of rice leaf scald disease as described in Japan were produced on leaf tips (photo 1). Each successive band was accompanied by narrow, light-brown halos. The average lesion was 2.58 cm long, ranging from 1-4.5 cm. Five to 10% of the leaf area was infected.

The fungus, when isolated in pure culture, produced luxuriant white growth on potato dextrose agar amended with 2% hot water extract of rice leaf (PDE) and copious bicelled, slightly falcate conidia within 4-6 days of incubation at 25±1°C (photo 2). The conidia were borne directly on the hyphae or on short conidiophores and they germinated readily in water within 6 hours of incubation at 25±1° C. The mean conidial size was 11.82 × 3.62 μ on the leaf lesions and 12.28 × 4.0 μ on PDE. The mycelium from the host tissue was hyaline, septate, and branched.

When artificially inoculated on the susceptible rice cultivar Jaya, the fungus produced typical leaf-tip blight, reddish-brown lesions on the leaf sheath, and

water-soaked lesions (like those of rice leaf scald disease) on the margins of the leaf blade.

A culture of the fungus, sent to the Commonwealth Mycological Institute, Kew, England, was confirmed as *R. oryzae*. This is the first report of a collateral host for *R. oryzae*. ■

Survey of rice nematodes in deepwater rice fields

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A survey of parasitic nematodes in deepwater rice fields was conducted in Thailand from January 1979 to January 1980.

Samples of soil and plant materials were collected from farmers' fields at nine sites in Ayuthaya and two in Prajinburi province at four times: before planting, before the floodwaters rose (about 45 days after seeding), after the floodwaters receded (about 3 mo after seeding), and at harvest.

Each sample was randomly collected from four spots in a field and then composited. Nematodes were extracted from soil, roots, and leaves by Baermann's funnel technique and identified at the Plant Pathology Division. The genera identified are listed in Table 1.

Only *Hirschmanniella*, *Tylenchorhynchus*, and *Meloidogyne* were abundant in the soil. They represented 11.4, 41.5, and 47.1% of the total population sampled (Table 2). *Hirschmanniella* was abundant in the

1. Symptoms produced on the grass host *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) Beauv.